

Global Observations of Sporadic-E and Spread-F Occurrence Rates Using the COSMIC-2 Constellation

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Abstract

We observed the presence of ionospheric L-band Sporadic-E and Spread-F occurrence during 2020-2022 using the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate – 2 (COSMIC-2) also known as FORMOSAT-7. We used the reported S4 scintillation index, an indicator of the scintillation along the line-of-sight, and following previous studies, geolocated the scintillation to the tangent ray height of the line-of-sight between the COSMIC-2 satellite and the Global Positioning System satellite. We then produced maps of the scintillation occurrence frequency versus season and time of day. Our results are in agreement with prior studies using the COSMIC-1 satellites, but some features are more clearly seen in our study.

Introduction

The ionosphere is a very dynamic region of the Earth's atmosphere. It is strongly driven by forcing external to the Earth's atmosphere. Photonic input from both solar and extra-solar sources drives the ionization in the ionosphere and heats the atmosphere driving winds. High energy particle precipitation in the auroral zones provides another source of ionization and also heats the thermosphere, which affects thermospheric winds thereby driving ionospheric dynamics. Solar driven tides due to atmospheric heating in the troposphere also generate driving wind fields, which are particularly important as drivers of layering in the E-region ionosphere. The “fountain effect” caused by the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift, due to the zonal electric field, causes uplift of the plasma at low magnetic latitudes. Once the uplift ceases, the plasma can drift back down the magnetic field lines under the influence of gravity and neutral wind drag. Waves and tides propagating upward from the troposphere also can perturb the plasma density. These waves can drive ionospheric waves such as medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances, mountain waves, ionospheric bubbles and depletions. Thus, ionospheric dynamics varies both geographically and in time. The external forcing is best characterized in terms of the universal time, because solar flares, for example, occur without regard to the location of the Sun with respect to the Earth. The internal forcing is better characterized by the Solar Local Time (SLT), because much of the heating and tropospheric dynamics are driven by the Sun's location overhead. To better understand the types of structures present at different locations on the Earth and how they impact the ionosphere, we performed our studies in terms of universal time and solar local time.

This paper describes our assessments of how the S4 scintillation index as measured by the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate – 2 (COSMIC-2) also known as FORMOSAT-7 [Schreiner *et al.*, 2020; Anthes and Schreiner, 2019] satellites varies

seasonally versus time of day. We performed inversions of all of the occultations to infer the electron density versus altitude and we used results of the occultation inversions to generate 3D data cubes (longitude, latitude, UT, SLT) by averaging the COSMIC-2 data into $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ (lat./lon.) bins. We also generated 3D data cubes of the S4 index on the same spatial and temporal grid. *This study used the S4 index from the COSMIC-2 data files geolocated to the tangent points of the lines-of-sight.* We used measurements where the $S4 > 0.5$, indicating severe scintillation, and binned the data into 3 hour intervals (to improve statistics) and made maps. This mapping was done in two altitude regimes; the F-region, $200 < Z < 600$ km, and E-region, $80 < Z < 160$ km. The S4 index is defined by [Retterer, 2010]:

$$S4 = \frac{\sqrt{\langle I^2 \rangle - \langle I \rangle^2}}{\langle I \rangle^2}$$

where I is the signal amplitude and the $\langle \rangle$ represents a time average, for the COSMIC satellites this is 1 second. The COSMIC measurements have proved to be surprisingly sensitive to L-band scintillation even during solar minimum, when previous ground-based studies have observed weak or non-existent scintillation at GHz frequencies. The COSMIC-2 POD TEC data were downloaded from the COSMIC Data Analysis and Archive Center (CDAAC) website at UCAR [https://data.cosmic.ucar.edu/gnss-ro/cosmic2/nrt/level1b/]. Each day of data was saved as a TARBALL. We downloaded ALL of 2020-2022 data -- a total of ~7.8 M occultations were used for this study.

Five types of maps were made: monthly average maps vs. Universal Time (UT); monthly average maps vs. Solar Local Time (SLT); quarterly average maps vs. UT; quarterly average maps vs. SLT; and quarterly average maps vs. SLT for the entire 2020-2022 period to be used as climatologies. We also assessed the relationship between the electron density and the S4 index, to see if it was possible to infer simple relationship similar to what *Arras and Wickert [2018]* found. Lastly, we compared the F-region scintillation observations to observations made by the GOLD mission [Eastes et al., 2017]. This paper is a preliminary report on the results of our research but will focus on the maps versus SLT. The full scope of our study will be the topic of a future publication.

Approach

We performed non-negative least-squares inversions of the COSMIC-2 radio occultations using the Least-Squares Positive Definite (LSPD) algorithm described in *Dymond, Budzien and Hei [2017]* to calculate the electron densities. The Total Electron Content (TEC) along a line-of-sight is given by:

$$T = 10^{-12} \int_0^\infty \varepsilon(z, \lambda, \phi) ds(z, \lambda, \phi)$$

where T is the TEC in units of TEC units (1 TEC Unit, TECU = 10^{12} electrons/cm²), ε is the electron density (electrons cm⁻³), λ is the latitude, ϕ is the longitude, z is the altitude, s is the distance (cm) along the line-of-sight, the constant, 10^{-12} , converts the units to TECU. When these

equations for the TEC during an occultation are taken together, they become a system of Fredholm integral equations of the first kind. These systems of equations are commonly solved using the Abel Inverse algorithm [for COSMIC see: *Anthes et al.*, 2008]; however, this algorithm can produce negative density values, which is a problem in the E-region ionosphere and can hide or mask the density layers that are of interest. In this study, we used a quadrature scheme based on Simpson's rule with equally spaced samples along the lines-of-sight [*Press et al.*, 1992] from the COSMIC satellite to the top of the ionosphere in the direction toward the Global Position Satellite being observed. Along a given line-of-sight, the sample spacing was constant, but the spacing varied along different lines-of-sight. The electron density was approximated by local cubic polynomials assuming that the local electron density was spherically symmetric and only varied with altitude. Thus, at a given sample point along the line-of-sight, the electron density was a function of the four nearest neighbor points in altitude. The integral above was replaced by:

$$T_i = 10^{-12} \sum_n W(z_{i,n}, z_g) \varepsilon(z_g) \Delta s_{i,n}$$

where $\Delta s_{i,n}$ is the Simpson's rule path-length along the i^{th} line-of-sight, $z_{i,n}$ is the tangent ray height of the ray, z_g is the altitude grid for the ionosphere, and $W(z_{i,n}, z_g)$ is the weight matrix containing contributions from the Simpson's rule weights and the relative weighting of the point on the line-of-sight based on the local cubic-spline interpolant weight. This system of equations was written in conventional matrix notation:

$$Ax = b$$

where A is the product of the W matrix and the Δs vector or the path-length matrix, x is the volume emission rate recast as a vector, and b is the TEC vector, T . We solve this system in the least-squares sense so that measurement errors can be used to find the most probable solution subject to the measurement uncertainties by minimizing the chi-squared statistic, χ^2 :

$$\chi^2 = (Ax - b)^T \Sigma_D^{-1} (Ax - b)$$

This is minimized when the partial derivatives of χ^2 with respect to x_i are zero, yielding the following matrix equation:

$$(A^T \Sigma_D^{-1} A)x = A^T \Sigma_D^{-1} b$$

where Σ_D^{-1} is the inverse covariance matrix:

$$\Sigma_D^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sigma_i^2 & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & 1/\sigma_n^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 1: Electron Density Comparison. The results of an inversion the TEC from a single occultation are compared. The black curve indicates the density from an Abel Inversion. The red asterisks indicate the density derived from the LSPD inversion. The Abel Inverse results are on the altitude grid from the tangent points of the occultation, while the LSPD results are on a fixed altitude grid with 72 exponentially distributed points running from 70-500 km.

The diagonal elements of this matrix are the reciprocals of the squares of the uncertainties of each of the measurements. This system of equations can be solved using the LSPD algorithm to produce non-negative electron densities on the common model grid z_g . Once the electron density solution was obtained, the S4 index values reported in the COSMIC-2 data files were interpolated to the same altitude grid as the electron density inversions – a fixed logarithmic grid with 74 cells covering altitudes from 60-650 km. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the electron density derived by Abel inversion of an occultation and by the inversion of the occultation using the technique presented here. The agreement is excellent. The black line in the figure shows the Abel density, while the red asterisks show the result of the LSPD inversion. The advantages of the LSPD approach are that it is computationally faster, non-negative, and the inversions are on a common altitude grid enabling straightforward binning to produce the 4-dimensional data cubes.

Once the S4 index and electron density were calculated as functions of altitude, the results were binned into four dimensional grids. The altitude grid is that stated above. The longitude and latitude grid spacing was 5° . These data were then re-binned temporally to create the data cubes. The maps were then created by summing over altitude: the F-region, $200 < Z < 600$ km, and E-region, $80 < Z < 160$ km.

Results and Discussion

Quarterly Averages vs. SLT: Figures 2 and 3, show maps of the quarterly scintillation frequencies for October-December of 2020-2022. The maps show the S4 occurrence frequencies for 3 hour SLT bins: Panel (a) 0-3 SLT; panel (b) 3-6 SLT; panel (c) 6-9 SLT; panel (d) 9-12 SLT; panel (e)

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Figure 2: F-region Quarterly Average Occurrence Frequency. The average occurrence frequency for high F-region scintillation during October-December of 2020-2022 is plotted versus SLT in 3 hour bins. Panel (a) 0-3 SLT; panel (b) 3-6 SLT; panel (c) 6-9 SLT; panel (d) 9-12 SLT; panel (e) 12-15 SLT; panel (f) 15-18 SLT; panel (g) 18-21 SLT; and panel (h) 21-24 SLT.

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Figure 3: E-region Quarterly Average Occurrence Frequency. The average occurrence frequency for high E-region scintillation during October-December of 2020-2022 is plotted versus SLT time in 3 hour bins. Panel (a) 0-3 SLT; panel (b) 3-6 SLT; panel (c) 6-9 SLT; panel (d) 9-12 SLT; panel (e) 12-15 SLT; panel (f) 15-18 SLT; panel (g) 18-21 SLT; and panel (h) 21-24 SLT.

12-15 SLT; panel (f) 15-18 SLT; panel (g) 18-21 SLT; and panel (h) 21-24 SLT. Note that the color scales change from panel-to-panel to better capture the structures in a given image. Figure 2 shows the F-region frequencies while Figure 3 shows the E-region frequencies. Panel 2a, shows the F-region frequency is highest over Eastern South America and then drops off in panel 2b and little scintillation is observed in the F-region in panels 2c-2e. Panel 2f shows the scintillation rate to be increasing over North-Eastern South America, with some additional activity over India. Panels 2g and 2h show strong enhancements in the scintillation frequency over South America and extending out over the Atlantic Ocean; this is consistent with bubble imagery observed by the GOLD [Eastes *et al.*, 2017] mission. Note that the F-region S4 occurrence frequencies are highest between $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes, shown by the aqua colored lines in the panels of Figure 2. Panel 3a, shows the E-region frequency is highest over Eastern South America coincident with the F-region frequency of occurrence in Figure 2a. This is of interest because this may suggest a common source of the scintillations in both the E- And F-regions, possibly orographic waves generated by turbulence over the Andes Mountains. The frequency drops off in panel 3b but the occurrence rate of scintillations has increased at low latitudes globally. Panels 3c-3f show consistent E-region scintillation during the sunlit hours at low latitudes globally, which is consistent with the scintillations being generated by the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability in areas where there is some E-region layering. Panels 3g and 3h shows the scintillation rate to be increasing over South America and over the Atlantic Ocean at nighttime. This is surprising as previous studies had not indicated the presence of nighttime scintillation in the E-region. The presence of higher occurrence frequencies in this region is consistent with bubble imagery observed by the GOLD [Eastes *et al.*, 2017] mission. This might suggest that the E- and F-region scintillations have a common source at night: formation of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability at low altitudes when the ionospheric Spread-F depletions are present or beginning to form. We note that similar correlations between the E-region and F-region high frequency regions was observed in all seasons in the 3 year quarterly averages.

Monthly Averages vs. SLT: Figures 4, 5, and 6 show maps of the monthly scintillation statistics for March of 2020-2022. The maps show the daily/monthly average statistics: Panel (a) E-region occurrence frequency; panel (b) the average S4 value in the E-region; panel (c) the average S4 altitude in the E-region; panel (d) the average S4 value in the F-region; panel (e) the average S4 altitude in the F-region; and panel (f) the average S4 altitude in the E-region. Figure 4 shows the statistics for March 2020. Note the contrast between the occurrence frequency images versus those in Figures 5 and 6. The images in Figures 4, 5, and 6 show a much more uniform rate of occurrence with longitude than was observed in Figures 2 and 3; this is caused by the averaging over all SLTs smoothing out the daily variations in the dynamics driving the scintillations. Note that all three metrics are increasing through from 2020-2022. The occurrence frequencies in 2021 are 3-5 times higher than they were in 2020 and are 2-3 times higher in 2022 than they were in Mar 2021. The numbers of occultations per day increased by factors of ~ 1.4 -1.8 because additional observations of other GPS-like satellites, GLONASS and BEIDOU for example, were also included, but this not entirely the cause. This is most likely due to the solar activity increasing during this time interval. When the other months are considered October-December shows the highest overall occurrence rate of scintillation in both the E- and F-regions during all three years. This activity also tends to be clustered between magnetic latitudes of $\pm 20^\circ$ N. There also appears to be a higher frequency of E-region scintillation in the northern hemisphere during May-August than in the Southern hemisphere.

Figure 4: March 2020 S4 Statistics. Panels a, b, and c show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the E-region (60-160 km). Panels d, e, and f show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the F-region (200-400 km).

COSMIC-1/COSMIC-2 Comparison: Figure 7 shows a comparison of the daily average scintillation occurrence frequencies for COSMIC-1 versus COSMIC-2. Panel (a) shows the COSMIC-1 F-region occurrence rate for April 2007 from [Dymond, 2012]. Panel (c) shows the sum of the occurrence rate over latitude with the positive values indicating the Northern

Figure 5: March 2021 S4 Statistics. Panels a, b, and c show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the E-region (80-160 km). Panels d, e, and f show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the F-region (200-400 km). Note that all of the statistics are higher than they were in March 2020.

hemisphere, while the negative values indicate the Southern hemisphere. Panel (b) shows the COSMIC-1 F-region occurrence rate for April 2020. Note that the 2007 map is at 15° longitude resolution, while the 2020 map is at 5°. At both times, the scintillation frequencies increased over

Figure 6: March 2022 S4 Statistics. Panels a, b, and c show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the E-region (80-160 km). Panels d, e, and f show the Occurrence Frequency, Average S4 Value, and Average Altitude of the S4 peak value for the F-region (200-400 km). Note that all of the statistics are higher than they were in March 2020 and 2021.

the Pacific Ocean. However, during 2007 the highest scintillation frequencies occurred over Africa, while in 2020 they are occurring off the West Coast of South America. The cause of this difference is not known at this time, but suggests additional research is needed.

Figure 7: COSMIC-1/COSMIC-2 Comparison: Panel (a) shows the COSMIC-1 F-region occurrence rate for April 2007. Panel (c) shows the total over of the occurrence rate latitude with the positive values indicating the Northern hemisphere, while the negative values indicate the Southern hemisphere [Dymond, 2012]. Panel (b) shows the COSMIC-2 F-region occurrence rate for April 2020.

Summary

We provided a preliminary discussion of our studies of E- and F-region scintillation using the COSMIC-2 constellation. We inverted ~ 7.8 million occultations using a positive definite least-squares inversion approach and a common altitude grid and interpolated the observed S4 index onto the same altitude grid. These results were then binned to produce four-dimensional data cubes (latitude, longitude, altitude, and time) and the results were used to make maps to explore the global distribution of the E- and F-region scintillation with time and season. No obvious spatial sampling issues were observed using COSMIC-2.

When displayed as a function of *Solar Local Time*, the scintillation probability maps showed: F-region production consistent with known Rayleigh-Taylor instability producing ionospheric bubbles, driven by orographic waves and tropospheric wave propagation. The E-region probability was consistently higher throughout the daytime hours than the F-region probability and tended to be higher in the afternoon and evening than it was in the morning, this is consistent with the production of molecular ions in the E-region being perturbed by the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability to produce the scintillation. The E-region scintillation tended to be more widely distributed geographically than F-region scintillation, which tended to peak between $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. Typical mean altitudes for the E-region scintillation are 80-110 km, while the F-region scintillation tends to occur toward the bottom of the F-region, at altitudes of 250-300 km.

When the scintillation statistics for March 2020, 2021, and 2022 were compared to each other, the scintillation frequency and strength increased each year, which is consistent with the increasing solar activity levels as solar maximum is approached. When other months were compared, it was found that October-December showed the highest overall occurrence rate of scintillation in both

the E- and F-regions. The F-region scintillation also tended to be clustered between magnetic latitudes of $\pm 20^\circ$. There also appears to be a higher frequency of E-region scintillation in the northern hemisphere during May-August than in the Southern hemisphere. The mean altitude of the scintillation increased as did the mean S4 strength. These increases are most likely due to the solar activity increasing during this time interval.

The COSMIC-1 and COSMIC-2 F-region scintillation frequencies of occurrence were compared for April 2007 and April 2020. During 2007 the highest scintillation frequencies occurred over Africa, while in 2020 they occurred off the West Coast of South America. The cause of this difference is not known at this time, but suggests additional research is needed.

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